

3D-printed matrices for the purification of plasmid DNA *via* steric exclusion chromatography

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ABSTRACT

Plasmid DNA (pDNA) holds great promise not only for gene therapy and DNA vaccination, but also as a raw material to produce mRNA and viral vaccines. However, achieving high-quality pDNA purification remains a significant challenge. Current purification methods, often involving multiple precipitation and chromatographic steps, can compromise the structural integrity and stability of the desired supercoiled (sc) pDNA isoform, which is crucial for effective gene transfer.

This work aims to explore the potential of steric exclusion chromatography (SXC) as a novel approach for capturing pDNA, immediately after cell lysis, and using 3D-printed chromatographic matrices. The experimental workflow includes cultivation of *Escherichia coli* cells, harboring the model plasmid pVAX-eGFP (3696 bp), product release by alkaline lysis, and pDNA capture and purification in a single chromatographic step by SXC on 3D-printed hydrophilic supports. The influence of polyethylene glycol (PEG) molecular weights (1500 to 8000 Da) and concentrations (5 to 15 %) on pDNA retention was systematically explored. Total pDNA capture was achieved either employing short PEG chains at high concentrations or longer PEG chains at lower concentrations. Under optimized conditions, the process consistently achieved >97 % supercoiled (sc) pDNA total purity and allowed an 80 % reduction in host cell proteins (HCP).

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that SXC, implemented on 3D-printed hydrophilic monoliths, significantly mitigates the relaxation effects in plasmids observed in current purification procedures required for isolating sc pDNA, making it a promising and innovative approach for the development of a fast, high-capacity, and cost-effective pDNA capture step.

1. Introduction

Plasmid DNA (pDNA) serves dual critical roles in modern biotechnology as both a therapeutic agent and a foundational starting material [1]. As biological drugs, DNA vaccines utilize pDNA to deliver antigen-encoding sequences directly into host cells, triggering immune responses against pathogens or cancers without requiring live vectors [2,3]. Beyond direct therapeutic use, pDNA is indispensable for engineering animal cells to produce advanced biologics: it acts as a template for *in vitro* transcription (IVT) to generate mRNA vaccines and therapies [4,5],

provides the genetic backbone for viral vector production (e.g., lentiviral or AAV vectors) used in gene therapy [6–8], and enables siRNA synthesis for targeted gene silencing [9,10]. In particular, the supercoiled conformation of pDNA is essential for these applications [11,12], ensuring efficient transcription, stability during manufacturing, and compliance with regulatory standards of purity (> 80 % supercoiled content) [1,13].

The biomanufacturing of pDNA typically follows a two-phase procedure. The initial phase, referred to as upstream processing, consist mainly of plasmids replication typically in a recombinant *Escherichia coli*

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host through fermentation [14–16]. The subsequent steps involve downstream processing (DSP) and aim to separate and purify pDNA from cellular debris and various impurities, such as RNA, host cell proteins (HCP), and genomic DNA (gDNA), in order to obtain pDNA with sufficient purity to meet pharmaceutical standards [17,18]. DSP often involves several precipitation and chromatographic steps, leading not only to time-consuming and expensive production, but also impacting the stability and structural integrity of the plasmid, leading to its degradation. This has a significantly negative impact on the purity and yield of the final pDNA product, with the relaxed isoforms becoming predominant [14,19,20]. In addition, chromatographic separations represent up to 70 % of pDNA biomanufacturing costs, driven by time-consuming and labor-intensive batch processes and expensive adsorbents [21–23].

Among the emerging alternatives for large biomolecules purification, steric exclusion chromatography (SXC) has gained attention as a gentle and cost-effective technique [24,25]. Its principle relies on the mutual exclusion of a crowding polymer, typically polyethylene glycol (PEG), from a large target solute (e.g., pDNA) and a hydrophilic solid phase, forcing these two large entities into closer proximity. In contrast, small solutes (e.g., proteins, RNA) are less affected and flow through the column without being retained. Elution of retained solutes can be achieved by reducing the PEG concentration [24,26].

The molecular mechanism underlying SXC closely mirrors that of PEG-induced precipitation, as both are governed by excluded-volume effects. The addition of PEG reduces the solvent space available for large biomolecules, increasing their effective concentration and driving phase separation (in precipitation) or adsorption (in SXC). This is an entropically driven process that depends strongly on PEG molecular weight and concentration with larger PEG chains and higher concentrations generally enhancing exclusion and retention. Nevertheless, excessive PEG concentrations increase viscosity, hindering solute diffusion and mass transfer, and generating shear forces that can lead to column pressure limitations [25].

These viscosity-related constraints emphasize the need for convective media such as monoliths [27–29], membranes [30,31] and fibers [32] enable efficient solute transport through large interconnected pores. Their convective flow regime mitigates diffusional resistance and allows higher flow rates without excessive backpressure, making them particularly suitable for PEG-containing systems [30,33,34].

Recently, Conti et al. addressed the need for tunable porous stationary phases by introducing 3D-printed porous adsorbents fabricated from methacrylate-based inks, incorporating the epoxy-based monomer glycidyl methacrylate (GMA) [35]. This one step 3D-printing approach allows the design of monoliths with controlled porosity, geometry, and surface chemistry, offering precision, repeatability, and customization, promising faster and more economical therapeutic production suitable for a broad range in DSP applications [35–37].

In this work, we aim to explore the application of the bespoke 3D-printed chromatographic matrices for steric exclusion chromatography (SXC) as a streamline strategy for capturing pDNA directly from the clarified cell lysates. By leveraging the customizable pore architecture and high permeability of 3D-printed supports, we aim to overcome the mass transfer and pressure limitations typically associated with viscous PEG-containing buffers [24,25,38,39]. We systematically evaluate the impact of PEG molecular weight and concentration on pDNA retention and separation performance. This approach seeks to simplify the purification process while preserving the structural integrity of the supercoiled isoform, addressing a major bottleneck in current downstream processing of plasmids [14,19]. Ultimately, our goal is to establish a single-step, high-efficiency, and scalable platform for pDNA purification that minimizes relaxation and degradation, offering a promising alternative to conventional multistep protocols.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

All chemicals were of analytical grade. Different molecular weight PEGs were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA).

2.2. Bacterial cell growth and plasmid production

A pre-inoculum was prepared from frozen DH5 α cells harboring pVAX-eGFP (3696 bp) [40] in 100 mL shake flasks containing 20 mL of LB medium (NZYTech, Lisbon, Portugal) supplemented with 30 μ g/mL kanamycin (Amresco, Solon, OH, US). Following overnight incubation at 250 rpm and 37 °C, cells were used to inoculate 2 L shake flasks containing 250 mL of LB medium with 30 μ g/mL kanamycin at an optical density at 600 nm (OD_{600nm}) of approximately 0.1. Cells were incubated at 37 °C, 250 rpm and harvested after 6 h by centrifugation (6000 g, 15 min).

2.3. Alkaline lysis

The alkaline method used was based on the protocol described by Birnboim et al. [41]. Briefly, cells harvested at the end of cell culture were resuspended in a 50 mM glucose, 25 mM Tris-HCl, 10 mM EDTA, pH 8, buffer up to an OD_{600nm} of 60 and mixed with a buffer composed of 0.2 M NaOH, 1 % (w/v) SDS at a 1:1 volume ratio. The mixture was gently homogenized and left to rest at room temperature for 10 min, after which a volume of 5 M acetate buffer with 3 M potassium (pH 5) equal to half of the mixture volume was added. After a second gentle homogenization, the neutralized lysate was placed on ice and left to rest for 10 min. A clarified lysate was then obtained by centrifugation (2 times at 15,000 g and 4 °C for 30 min).

2.4. 3D-printed monolith manufacturing

Monolithic chromatography supports were fabricated using digital light processing (DLP) technology with a W2P Solflex 350 DLP printer (385 nm, W2P, Vienna, Austria), as previously described [35]. Briefly, the printing process involved layer-by-layer polymerization of a custom-formulated ink containing 50 % (w/w) pore-forming agents (cyclohexanol/dodecanol 80/20), 10 % (w/w) dipentaerythritol pentaacrylate (SR399), 24 % (w/w) glycidyl methacrylate (GMA), and 16 % (w/w) ethylene glycol dimethylacrylate (EDMA). Photoinitiator (Omnirad 819, 1.5 g) and photoadsorber (Omnistab 326, 0.125 g) were added per 100 g of ink. All components were printed at a 50 μ m layer thickness with a 5.2-s exposure per layer.

Following printing, monoliths were washed with ethanol and post-cured using a OTOFLASH G171 unit (1000 flashes, NK-Optik, Baierbrunn, Germany). To enhance hydrophilicity, epoxy groups were hydrolyzed by incubating the monoliths in 100 mM H₂SO₄ at 50 °C for three days.

2.5. Preliminary PEG precipitation studies

Several PEG precipitation experiments were conducted to assess the efficiency and kinetics of PEG precipitation under concentrations ranging between 2 % and 20 % (w/v) and PEG molecular weights ranging between 400 and 8000 Da. In a 2 mL Eppendorf tube, 1 mL of lysate was combined with the appropriate volume of PEG. Subsequently, the samples were allowed to precipitate overnight, after which they were centrifuged at 14,000 g for 30 min. The supernatant was then discarded, and the pellet was resuspended in 100 μ L of TE buffer solution (10 mM Tris, 1 mM EDTA, pH 8).

2.6. Steric exclusion chromatography (SXC)

1 mL of the plasmid-containing solution obtained after alkaline lysis was conditioned to match the equilibrium conditions immediately before loading it into the column by the addition of 1 M NaCl solution along with the volume of PEG needed for the target concentration being tested for each PEG molecular weight. The total volume of the injected sample corresponded to 2 mL.

The supercoiled (sc) pDNA was then purified by steric exclusion chromatography either using a 0.7 mL 3D-printed monolithic column or a 0.7 mL Sepharose CL-6B (Cytiva) connected to an ÄKTApurifier10 system (Cytiva). The mobile phase consisted of mixtures of buffer A (20 % (w/v) PEG solution in 10 mM Tris, 1 M NaCl pH 8) and buffer B (10 mM Tris, 1 M NaCl, pH 8). The absorbance of the eluate was continuously measured at 260 nm by a UV detector positioned after the column outlet and the system was operated at 1 mL/min. The column was equilibrated with 5 column volumes (CV) at the desired concentration of PEG. Then, 2 mL of the conditioned sample was injected into the column by washing the loop with 6 mL of equilibration buffer. Unbound material was washed out of the column with 4 CV of equilibration buffer. Gradient elution was then performed for 20 CV up to 100 % B followed by a 2 mL gradient delay. The eluate was collected during the chromatographic run as 1.5 mL fractions.

2.7. Analytical methods

After SXC, the eluted samples were concentrated by PEG precipitation. PEG was added to each sample to achieve a final concentration of 15 %, followed by overnight incubation at 4 °C. The samples were then centrifuged at 14,000 g for 30 min. After discarding the supernatant, the resulting pellet was resuspended in 200 µL of TE buffer and subsequently analysed by agarose gel electrophoresis, HPLC for plasmid quantification, and BCA assay for protein concentration.

2.7.1. Gel electrophoresis

Agarose gels were prepared with 1 % (w/v) agarose (Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA) in TAE buffer (40 mM Tris-base, 20 mM acetic acid and 1 mM EDTA, pH 8) and loaded with samples mixed with 6× purple loading dye (New England Biolabs, MA), using NZYDNA ladder III (NZYTech, Lisbon, Portugal) as molecular weight marker. Gel electrophoresis was performed in TAE buffer at 90 V for 60 min. Gels were pre-stained with an ethidium bromide solution (0.625 mg/mL) and images were obtained with an Axygen Gel Documentation System. The percentage of sc pDNA on the purified fractions collected from the elution peak was determined by densitometry analysis of the band intensities on the agarose gel, using Fiji software.

2.7.2. Plasmid quantification

Samples collected during the chromatographic runs were analysed by analytical hydrophobic interaction chromatography (HIC)-HPLC to quantify pDNA, following the protocol described in [20,42]. Briefly, 1.7 mL bed volume (SOURCE 15 PHE 4.6/100 PE, Cytiva) connected to an ÄKTApurifier10 system (Cytiva), was equilibrated at 1 mL/min with 1.5 M ammonium sulphate in 10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8. Following column loading with 50 µL of sample under analysis, elution was performed in a step mode with 10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.

2.7.3. Protein quantification

Protein removal was determined using the bicinchoninic acid (BCA) protein assay reagent kit from Thermo Scientific (Waltham, MA) following the manufacturer's instructions. Bovine serum albumin (BSA) calibration solutions were prepared by serial dilution of a 2 mg/mL albumin standard in a concentration range from 0 to 2 mg/mL. 25 µL of each calibration solution and sample replicate were added to a 96-well plate, followed by the addition and mixing of 200 µL of working reagent (50 parts of reagent A to 1 part of reagent B). Then, the plate was

incubated for 30 min at 37 °C, after which they were cooled down to room temperature and the absorbance at 562 nm of all samples in analysis was measured within 10 min.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Precipitation studies

In 1978, Miekka and Ingham established that higher PEG concentrations robustly enhance precipitation efficiency for proteins [43], a finding later extended to nucleic acids through observation of similar trends in bulk PEG-driven fractionation [44].

SXC can be considered an adaptation of PEG precipitation that incorporates a stationary phase (in this case a monolith), providing an interface where the PEG-deficient zone facilitates specific retention and subsequent elution in a bind-and-elute chromatographic workflow. Recognizing these similarities, preliminary PEG precipitation studies were conducted to guide the development of the chromatographic process (Fig. 1). This approach enabled an early screening to narrow down the range of PEG molecular weights and concentrations experiments to be explored further in the SXC experiments.

Different PEG molecular weights (400 to 8000 Da) and concentrations (2 to 20 % (w/v)) were evaluated using clarified lysates. As shown in Fig. 1, total DNA precipitation increased with PEG molecular weight and concentration up to an optimum range, beyond which the yield slightly decreased. This trend reflects the balance between excluded-volume enhancement and viscosity-related limitations: while higher PEG concentrations increase the driving force for precipitation, excessive polymer levels promote overlap and interpenetration of PEG coils, which reduce the effective excluded volume per molecule and thus weaken the exclusion effect. Simultaneously, the higher viscosity hampers mass transfer and can lead to incomplete phase separation.

The chromatographic behavior of pDNA in the following SXC experiments was not evaluated for PEG-400 due to its poor precipitation efficiency. Also, a 2 % PEG concentration was discarded in further SXC experiments as this did not result in any notable precipitation effect.

3.2. Steric exclusion chromatography with 3D-printed monoliths

The subsequent set of experiments aimed to assess the suitability of 3D-printed chromatography matrices for testing the fundamental hypothesis that pDNA can be retained and purified immediately after cell lysis through steric exclusion induced by PEG.

The fabricated monoliths exhibited a highly porous morphology, with an average pore diameter of approximately 800 nm and an interconnected microporous structure ranging from 1 to 5 µm, promoting convective mass transport. The formulation was optimized for both mechanical stability and chromatographic efficiency through the inclusion of EDMA as a cross-linker and SR399 as a multi-functional cross-linker. The tailored porogen system increased surface area and improved separation efficiency. The resulting hydrophilic porous discs served as the stationary phase.

Immediately prior to sample injection, the clarified lysate solution was mixed off-line with a PEG-containing buffer to pre-condition the sample feed. The viscosity of the binding buffer is directly influenced by both PEG molecular weight and concentration. In particular, an increase in either PEG molecular weight or concentration results in a corresponding increase in the buffer's viscosity [24].

In the next series of experiments, the NaCl concentration was kept constant (1M), while the effects of PEG molecular weight and concentration (5 %, 8 %, 10 %, 12 % and 15 %,) on the pDNA retention were systematically investigated. All tests were conducted using a 3D-printed monolith with a bed volume of 0.7 mL.

3.2.1. PEG-1500

As a first attempt to isolate pDNA from RNA and other cell-related

Fig. 1. Total DNA precipitation with different PEG molecular weights and concentrations (2, 5, 8, 10, 15 and 20 % PEG from left to right). Error bars represent the standard deviation of 3 assays.

impurities, the performance of PEG-1500 was tested. The resulting chromatograms (Fig. 2A and S1) show that no elution peak was observed at 5 % and 8 % PEG concentrations. At 10 % PEG, elution occurred between 10 mL and 15 mL (Fig. 2B), while at 12 % PEG, the elution peak shifted to the 15 mL and 20 mL range. At 15 % PEG, the elution peak was observed just before reaching 20 mL. It is worth noting that, as PEG concentrations increase, retention volume (and consequently retention time) also increases, with elution peaks occurring later in the process. Indicating stronger retention of pDNA on the column.

To assess the performance of each condition, HPLC, BCA and densitometry analysis were conducted to assess the DNA recovery yield, protein removal efficiency and supercoiled percentage, respectively, across different PEG concentrations (Fig. 3).

According to Fig. 3A, DNA recovery yields ranged between 54 and 100 %. Furthermore, recovery reached 100 % at 12 % PEG and remained at 100 % at 15 % PEG, suggesting that the effect of increased PEG concentration on DNA retention plateaus beyond a certain point. Importantly, increasing PEG concentrations did not impair protein removal efficiency, which remained close to or above 90 % across all tested conditions. Densitometry analysis using FLJI software revealed a supercoiled pDNA purity of 98.1 % at 12 % of PEG, and of 100.0 % at 15 % PEG.

Fig. 3B confirms that a minimum of 10 % PEG-1500 is necessary to achieve pDNA binding to the column matrix. In all tested conditions, RNA species were detected exclusively in the flowthrough. At 12 % and

15 % PEG-1500, no pDNA can be detected in the flowthrough, confirming complete pDNA retention.

3.2.2. PEG-3350

To further investigate the impact of PEG molecular weight on pDNA retention and purification, PEG-3350 was also examined at concentrations ranging from 5 % to 15 %. The corresponding chromatograms (Fig. S2) show no observable elution peak at 5 % PEG. Nonetheless, clear elution peaks were recorded at 8 %, 10 %, 12 %, and 15 % PEG. As observed with PEG-1500, increasing PEG concentration led to delayed elution, reflecting stronger pDNA retention.

HPLC and BCA analyses was performed to assess DNA recovery yields protein removal efficiency, respectively (Fig. 4).

According to Fig. 4A, pDNA recovery yields ranged from 52.2 to 100 % with the highest recovery obtained at 10 % and 12 % PEG. Interestingly, DNA recovery significantly dropped to 58.2 % at 15 % PEG, likely due to the increased viscosities of the buffer at this PEG concentration, which may have hindered mass transfer through reduced film diffusion. At high PEG concentrations, interpenetration of PEG coils can further reduce the effective excluded volume per molecule, thereby weakening steric exclusion and decreasing overall recovery efficiency [24]. These results suggest that the beneficial effect of increasing PEG concentration reaches a plateau around 12 %, beyond which recovery may decline.

It is also observed that protein removal efficiency followed an opposite trend (Fig. 4A), with higher PEG concentrations (particularly

Fig. 2. Steric exclusion chromatography purification of sc pDNA using a linear gradient elution in a 0.7 mL 3D-printed monolith, with a mobile phase consisting of mixtures of buffer A (20 % (w/v) PEG-1500 in 10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8, 1 M NaCl) and buffer B (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8, 1 M NaCl). A) sc pDNA purification with equilibration at 8 % PEG-1500 concentration. B) sc pDNA purification with equilibration at 10 % PEG-1500 concentration.

A)

	PEG concentration (%)				
	5	8	10	12	15
pDNA recovery yield (%)	----	----	54.0	100.0	100.0
Protein removal efficiency (%)	----	----	88.9	89.2	90.3
sc pDNA purity (%)	----	----	97.4	98.1	100.0

B)

Fig. 3. A) Assessment of pDNA recovery yield (HIC-HPLC method), protein removal efficiency (BCA assay) and sc pDNA purity (densitometry analysis) for distinct chromatographic runs with varying PEG-1500 concentrations, using a 3D printed monolith with a bed volume of 0.7 mL. HIC-HPLC employed 50 μ L of each SXC-collected fraction for pDNA quantification, while 25 μ L of each sample was analysed for protein quantification. B) Agarose gel electrophoresis loaded with 20 μ L of each SXC-collected fraction from distinct chromatographic runs featuring varied PEG-1500 concentrations (5, 8, 10, 12 and 15 %). The gel includes the ladder (lane L), lysate solution feed (lane F), and samples corresponding to the flowthrough (lane FT) and the elution peak (lane EP).

A)

	PEG concentration (%)				
	5	8	10	12	15
pDNA recovery yield (%)	----	52.2	100.0	100.0	58.2
Protein removal efficiency (%)	----	88.2	82.3	75.3	85.4
sc pDNA purity (%)	----	89.6	97.8	97.0	97.6

B)

Fig. 4. A) Assessment of pDNA recovery yield (HIC-HPLC method), protein removal efficiency (BCA assay) and sc pDNA purity (densitometry analysis) expressed in % for distinct chromatographic runs with varying PEG-3350 concentrations, using a monolith with a bed volume of 0.7 mL. HIC-HPLC employed 50 μ L of each SXC-collected fraction for pDNA quantification, while 25 μ L of each sample was analysed for protein quantification. B) Agarose gel electrophoresis loaded with 20 μ L of each SXC-collected fraction from distinct chromatographic runs featuring varied PEG-3350 concentrations (5, 8, 10, 12 and 15 %). The gel includes the ladder (lane L), lysate solution feed (lane F), and samples corresponding to the flowthrough (lane FT) and the elution peak (lane EP).

10 % and 12 %) resulting in increased co-retention of proteins. This is likely due to enhanced steric exclusion effects that reduce the method's selectivity for pDNA over impurities [25].

In addition, a purity assessment was conducted using agarose gel electrophoresis (Fig. 4B). Accordingly, pDNA was present in the flowthrough at 8 % and 15 % PEG, confirming the incomplete retention and consequently lower yields at these concentrations. In contrast, no detectable pDNA was observed in the flowthrough at 10 % and 12 % PEG, supporting the complete retention of pDNA, as demonstrated by the 100 % yield. Densitometric analysis using FIJI software showed high supercoiled pDNA purity at PEG concentrations equal to 10 % and 12 %, with purity values of 97.8 % and 97.0 %, respectively.

3.2.3. PEG-6000

To further evaluate the influence of PEG molecular weight on plasmid purification, PEG-6000 was tested under the same conditions as in previous experiments. Notably, a 10 % PEG-6000 solution at 25 °C is more than four times as viscous as water, while a 20 % PEG-6000 solution is over eleven times more viscous [25].

The corresponding chromatograms (Fig. S3) show no detectable elution peak at 5 % PEG, however, distinct peaks are observed at higher concentrations, with later elution times corresponding to increasing PEG levels, a trend consistent with stronger retention.

HPLC analyses confirmed the presence of pDNA in the elution fractions, and BCA assay was performed to evaluate protein levels in the same fractions (Fig. 5).

According to Fig. 5A, the highest DNA recovery value (100 %) was achieved at PEG concentrations between 8 %, and 12 %, decreasing to 85.9 % at 15 %. This reduction likely reflects viscosity-related mass-transfer limitations and partial interpenetration of PEG coils at high PEG concentrations, both of which diminish the effective excluded volume and reduce pDNA capture efficiency. Additionally, protein impurities

were increasingly retained at higher PEG concentrations, particularly at 10 % and 12 %, likely due to intensified steric exclusion effects that reduce selectivity for pDNA [25].

Agarose gel electrophoresis (Fig. 5B) supported these findings. RNA species were consistently detected in the flowthrough, confirming effective separation of these impurities from the initial sample. Faint bands corresponding to relaxed pDNA isoforms were visible, yet the purity of the supercoiled form remained high, with values of 96.9 %, 97.2 %, and 96.2 % obtained at 8 %, 10 %, and 12 % PEG, respectively.

3.2.4. PEG-8000

In the final set of experiments, PEG-8000 was evaluated to assess the impact of even higher molecular weight PEG on pDNA retention and purity. According to the corresponding chromatograms (Fig. S4), elution peaks were detected at all PEG concentrations, with increasing retention time corresponding to higher PEG concentrations.

HPLC analysis confirmed that pDNA binding occurred even at 5 % PEG (Fig. 6A), with the highest DNA recovery value (100 %) achieved at 8 % PEG, followed by a decrease to 92.3 % at 10 % PEG. At 12 % and 15 % of PEG, however, reliable quantification was not possible due to quantification errors in the HPLC analysis, likely caused by the high viscosity of the samples. This raises doubts as to whether the apparent decrease in recovery at higher PEG concentrations is real or a consequence of impaired detection. As such, it remains unclear whether all PEGs truly follow the same trend of declining recovery with increasing concentration beyond an optimal concentration, or if the data at higher PEG concentrations are skewed by analytical limitations.

Furthermore, unlike with lower molecular weight PEGs, protein removal efficiency did not exhibit a consistent trend with PEG concentration, with protein removal efficiency remaining roughly around 80 %.

Purity analysis through agarose gel electrophoresis revealed that all RNA species were effectively removed from the initial sample across all

A)

	PEG concentration (%)				
	5	8	10	12	15
pDNA recovery yield (%)	----	100.0	100.0	100.0	85.9
Protein removal efficiency (%)	----	88.5	87.1	84.5	79.9
sc pDNA purity (%)	----	96.9	97.2	96.2	93.5

B)

Fig. 5. A) Assessment of pDNA recovery yield (HIC-HPLC method), protein removal efficiency (BCA assay) and sc pDNA purity (densitometry analysis) expressed in % for distinct chromatographic runs with varying PEG-6000 concentrations, using a monolith with a bed volume of 0.7 mL. HIC-HPLC employed 50 μ L of each SXC-collected fraction for pDNA quantification, while 25 μ L of each sample was analysed for protein quantification. B) Agarose gel electrophoresis loaded with 20 μ L of each SXC-collected fraction from distinct chromatographic runs featuring varied PEG-6000 concentrations (5, 8, 10, 12 and 15 %). The gel includes the ladder (lane L), lysate solution feed (lane F), and samples corresponding to the flowthrough (lane FT) and the elution peak (lane EP).

Fig. 6. A) Assessment of pDNA recovery yield (HIC-HPLC method), protein removal efficiency (BCA assay) and sc pDNA purity (densitometry analysis) expressed in % for distinct chromatographic runs with varying PEG-8000 concentrations, using a monolith with a bed volume of 0.7 mL. HIC-HPLC employed 50 μ L of each SXC-collected fraction for pDNA quantification, while 25 μ L of each sample was analysed for protein quantification. * represents the occurrence of quantification errors in the HPLC analysis. B) Agarose gel electrophoresis loaded with 20 μ L of each SXC-collected fraction from distinct chromatographic runs featuring varied PEG-8000 concentrations (5, 8, 10, 12 and 15 %). The gel includes the ladder (lane L), lysate solution feed (lane F), and samples corresponding to the flowthrough (lane FT) and the elution peak (lane EP).

conditions (Fig. 6B). However, relaxed pDNA isoforms (open circular and linear isoforms) became more prominent at this PEG molecular weight than with shorter PEGs, likely due to increased shear stress effects associated with high viscosities and pressure drops during chromatographic runs.

Despite achieving full recovery at 8 % PEG-8000, the purity of the supercoiled isoform was only 68.9 %. At 10 % PEG, which yielded the second highest pDNA recovery, sc pDNA purity improved to 76.0 %, but still fell short compared to lower molecular weights PEGs. These findings highlight the trade-off between retention strength and structural preservation of the plasmid.

Overall, while PEG-8000 enabled effective pDNA capture, the high viscosity associated with this polymer resulted in reduced purity and analytical uncertainty. These results support the preferential use of shorter PEG molecules, which offer lower viscosity, mitigating the risk of significant backpressure and shear stress while preserving plasmid integrity during SXC.

3.3. Steric exclusion chromatography with bead-based purification media

To compare the performance of the 3D-printed monoliths with conventional bead-based materials, a column was packed with 0.7 mL of Sepharose CL-6B. This resin was selected due to its hydrophilic character and lack of ligands on its surface, thus providing a suitable control for comparison. The optimal conditions regarding PEG molecular weight and concentration in the monolith study were selected and the experiments were run on the same conditions to ensure a direct comparison between the two matrices.

As seen in Fig. S5, the retention volume and, consequently, the

retention time are slightly higher when using a monolith in the chromatographic runs for 12 % PEG-1500 and 10 % PEG-3350. This difference may be due to the slightly larger diameter of the monolith (12 mm vs. 10 mm), which results in a decreased linear velocity.

Pressure levels were closely monitored throughout the experiments and a very high increase in backpressure was observed beyond the acceptable limits for the bead-based chromatography, which lead to resin collapse at higher PEG concentrations and molecular weights. This did not happen with the 3D-printed monoliths, where pressure remained constant for all the conditions.

Nevertheless, key performance metrics, such as DNA recovery yield, sc pDNA content and protein removal efficiency, were still calculated (Fig. 7). According to Fig. 7, the pDNA recovery yield decreases when comparing the 3D-printed monolith with the bead-based chromatography, for both tested conditions. More significantly, Fig. 7B shows that a considerable reduction in the intensity of the sc band is observed between the feed and the elution peak. This reduction suggests plasmid relaxation, likely attributed to the higher intrinsic superficial velocity and, consequently, higher shear stress. Indeed, the total purity of sc pDNA was notably low, reaching only 64.9 % and 26.7 % for the 12 % PEG-1500 and 10 % PEG-3350, respectively.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrated the successful application of SXC on 3D-printed monolithic columns for the one-step capture of supercoiled pDNA isoform directly from clarified lysate, with a high yield. Under optimized conditions – 12 % and 15 % PEG-1500, 10 % PEG-3350, and 8 % PEG-6000 – complete retention was achieved, yielding supercoiled

Fig. 7. A) Assessment of pDNA recovery yield (HIC-HPLC method), protein removal efficiency (BCA assay) and sc pDNA purity (densitometry analysis) expressed in % for chromatographic runs at 12 % PEG-1500 and 10 % PEG-3350, using a bead-based column with a bed volume of 0.7 mL. HIC-HPLC employed 50 μ L of each SXC-collected fraction for pDNA quantification, while 25 μ L of each sample was analysed for protein quantification. B) Agarose gel electrophoresis loaded with 20 μ L of each SXC-collected fraction from the two chromatographic runs. The gel includes the ladder (lane L), lysate solution feed (lane F), and samples corresponding to the flowthrough (lane FT) and the elution peak (lane EP).

isoform purities of 98.1 %, 100 %, 97.8 %, and 96.9 %, respectively. These conditions also yielded high protein removal efficiencies of 89.2 %, 90.3 %, 82.3 %, and 88.5 %, respectively, highlighting the selectivity of the method. The results clearly support the preference for shorter PEG molecules, which enable effective separation while minimizing buffer viscosity. This helps reduce backpressure and shear stress effects during processing, thereby preserving the structural integrity of the plasmid and avoiding relaxation effects, a key requirement for therapeutic applications.

Overall, this work establishes 3D-printed hydrophilic monoliths as a promising and customizable platform for SXC-based pDNA capture immediately after cell lysis. This approach effectively minimizes shear stress effects and reduces the risk of plasmid relaxation. The methodology offers a fast, high-capacity and cost-effective alternative to traditional multi-step downstream processes and may serve as a foundation for scalable purification protocols in gene therapy, DNA vaccination, and mRNA production workflows. Moreover, this approach based on 3D-printed matrices offer notable advantages in small- to medium-batch workflows, including rapid prototyping, customized geometries, and on-demand manufacturing capability, they present growing economic and operational advantages enabling reduced pressure drops, design flexibility and minimized warehouse costs.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

A. Rita Silva-Santos: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Joana Silva:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Sara Sousa Rosa:** Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Mariachiara Conti:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology. **James R. Pullen:** Writing – review & editing, Resources.

Simone Dimartino: Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology. **Ana M. Azevedo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have not known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2025.136556>.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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